

Bu qobiliyat tafakkurning eng yuqori shakllaridan biri bo‘lib, bilimni shakllantirish, qayta ishlash va tadbiiq etish jarayonlarining asosini tashkil etadi.

Tanqidiy fikrlash — bu ma’lumot va g‘oyalarni diqqat bilan tahlil qilish, baholash va ularga asoslangan holda xulosa chiqarish qobiliyatidir. Bu fikrlash uslubi insonga har qanday ma’lumotni to‘g‘ri anglash, haqiqatni yolg‘ondan ajratish, oqilona qarorlar qabul qilishda yordam beradi.

Kreativ (ijodiy) fikrlash — bu mavjud muammolarni yangi, nostandart, original yechimlar orqali hal qilishga qaratilgan fikrlash jarayonidir. U odatiy yo‘llardan chiqib, yangicha qarashlar, noodatiy yondshuvlar, yangi g‘oyalar va innovasion yechimlarni topish imkonini beradi.

Muammoli vaziyatlarni hal qilish qobiliyati – bu shaxsning turli muammo va vazifalarni tahlil qilish, ularning mohiyatini anglash va samarali yechim topish ko‘nikmasidir. U nafaqat nazariy bilimlarni, balki amaliyotda ulardan foydalanishni ham talab qiladi.

Mustaqil fikrlash – bu shaxsning voqea-hodisalarga, ma’lumotlarga va muammolarga boshqalarning ta’sirisiz, shaxsiy bilim, tajriba va mantiqiy xulosalariga tayana olgan holda yondashish qobiliyatidir.

Demak, intellektual qobiliyat insonning bilim olish, fikr yuritish va ijodiy faoliyatining asosiy poydevori hisoblanadi. Uning har bir tarkibiy qismi shaxsning tafakkur darajasi, ijodkorligi va hayotiy muammolarni hal qilish samaradorligini belgilaydi.

Endi biz multimedia texnologiyalarining ta’limdagi ahamiyatiga to‘xtalib o‘tamiz.

Multimedia texnologiyalari — bu matn, ovoz, video, animatsiya va grafika elementlarining uyg‘unlashuvi orqali axborotni taqdim etish vositalaridir. Ular ta’limda quyidagi imkoniyatlarni yaratadi:[3]

Multimedia texnologiyalarining ta’limdagi ahamiyati quyidagilardan iborat:

1. **Tushunarlilik va yorqinlik** – o‘quv materiallari matn bilan birga rasm, animatsiya va videolarda ifodalanganda, talabalar uchun ma’lumotni qabul qilish osonlashadi.
2. **Ilyustrativlik** – nazariy bilimlarni real hayotiy misollar orqali namoyish etish imkoniyatini beradi.
3. **Ijodkorlik va qiziqish uyg‘otish** – interaktiv dasturlar, o‘yinlar va simulyasiyalar orqali o‘quvchilarning qiziqishi ortib, bilimga bo‘lgan intilish kuchayadi.
4. **Muammoli vaziyatlarni modellashtirish** – multimedia vositalari orqali tajribani amalda ko‘rsatish yoki hodisani virtual tarzda namoyish qilish mumkin.
5. **Individuallashtirish** – har bir o‘quvchi o‘z imkoniyatiga qarab, turli formatlardagi ma’lumotni qabul qila oladi.
6. **Samaradorlik** – vaqtni tejaydi, chunki ko‘p ma’lumot siqilgan holda bir vaqtning o‘zida bir nechta kanal orqali qabul qilinadi (ko‘rish, eshitish, o‘ylash).
7. **Muloqot va hamkorlikni kuchaytirish** – interaktiv platformalar orqali o‘qituvchi va talabalar o‘rtasida faol aloqalar yo‘lga qo‘yiladi.

Multimedia texnologiyalari ta’lim jarayonini **qiziqarli, tushunarli, samarali va zamonaviy** qiladi. Ular talabalarning bilim olishini osonlashtirish, ijodkorlikni rivojlantirish va ta’lim sifatini oshirishda muhim ahamiyatga ega.[2]

Multimedia texnologiyalari orqali intellektual qobiliyatlarni rivojlantirish yo‘llari xam mavjut bo‘lib o‘qituvchilarining intellektual salohiyatini shakllantirishda quyidagi usullar samarali hisoblanadi:

Multimedia shakli	Intellektual qobiliyatga ta’siri
Animatsiyali videolar	Mantiqiy fikrlashni faollashtiradi

Multimedia shakli	Intellektual qobiliyatga ta'siri
Interaktiv testlar	Mushohada va tahlil ko'nikmalarini rivojlantiradi
Elektron platformalar	Mustaqil ta'lim va axborot tahlili qobiliyatini oshiradi
Simulyasiyalar va keys-stadi	Muammoli vaziyatda to'g'ri yechim topish qobiliyatini shakllantiradi

Multimedia texnologiyalari ta'lim jarayonini zamonaviy, qiziqarli va samarali qilib, talabalardagi intellektual qobiliyatlarni – ijodkorlik, mustaqillik, tanqidiy va mantiqiy fikrlashni hamda muammo hal qilish ko'nikmalarini shakllantiradi va rivojlantiradi.[5]

Didaktik tavsiyalar

1. Multimedia resurslarini tanlash va ularni ta'lim maqsadida samarali qo'llashni o'rgatish.
2. Multimedia kontentlarni pedagogik maqsadlarga muvofiq tanlash va tahrirlash ko'nikmalarini shakllantirish.
3. Amaliy mashg'ulotlarda interaktiv materiallardan foydalanishni kengaytirish.
4. Ta'lim jarayonini tahlil qilish va baholashda raqamli vositalardan foydalanish orqali refleksiv qobiliyatlarni rivojlantirish.

Xulosa.

Multimedia texnologiyalaridan maqsadli va metodik jihatdan to'g'ri foydalanish bo'lajak pedagoglarining intellektual qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirishda muhim omil hisoblanadi. Ta'lim jarayonini raqamlashtirish va axborot texnologiyalarini integratsiya qilish orqali pedagogik tayyorgarlikning sifatini oshirish imkoni yaratiladi.

Multimedia texnologiyalari asosida intellektual qobiliyatlarni rivojlantirish bo'lajak pedagoglari uchun katta didaktik imkoniyatlarni yaratadi. Ular nafaqat bilimlarni chuqur o'zlashtirish, balki mustaqil, ijodiy va tanqidiy fikrlay olish, muammolarni samarali hal qilish, innovasion yondashuvlarga ega bo'lish salohiyatini shakllantiradi. Shu bois, multimedia texnologiyalaridan foydalanish zamonaviy ta'lim jarayonining muhim talablaridan biri hisoblanadi.

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Abstract: This environment provides them with both linguistic information and material for creating their own speech system, which is understandable to others and necessary for communication. In short, children are literally immersed in a speech atmosphere from the moment they are born. The child's speech development depends greatly on the warmth and comfort of their home, the love and care provided by their mother, and the close emotional contact they have with her and other family members. This constant interaction with loved ones helps children learn and grow, as they are exposed to language and other stimuli that contribute to their speech development. The speech environment is not only shaped by the words spoken, but also by other sensory experiences such as light, color, smell, and touch. These factors create a rich and stimulating environment that supports the child's language learning.

Introduction

By using analogies with children, adults can help children with the aid of a psychotherapy group, which, according to K. E. Rudestam, “the beneficial effect one person has on another”, also tries to create for them a sense of family – a special community, the atmosphere of which, like in a good family, is filled with warmth, love and trust. In this case, we are also talking about empathy – a deep understanding and comprehension of another person's emotional state – which, in its maternal form, is natural in relation to children, but which is lacking in formal education and can be developed in adults. This quality is priceless in life as it opens up channels of perception, including interpersonal communication, and forms the basis for deep connection. Adults, like children, need emotional warmth and connection with others. This is especially important when a person is standing on the threshold of something new and unknown, which is exactly what our unique training program is about, and what each person will have to “immerse” themselves in and comprehend: foreign language speech. By agreeing to study in this group, a person not only finds himself among like-minded individuals who share his goals, dreams, worries, and hopes. He also receives their attention, comprehensive support, constant feedback, and an amazing opportunity to look at himself from an outside perspective. This is an amazing chance for him to thank his partners for their help and support with no less attention or care. The teacher in this “family” assumes the role of a “parent”, from whom not only words of information emanate, but also feelings of love, kindness, and warmth. Their goal is to create a world of bright colors and smiles in this “family”, a fertile ground on which the human soul can flourish like a delicate flower. And with it, a piece of that soul – speech, is shared. In addition, to creating a sense of family, this psychotherapeutic group also creates a model of society, where each member will acquire communication skills, especially speech. They will take on various social roles, honing their communication techniques and speech skills in the

process. This group is a small, closed-type group whose members are united by a shared goal and have close emotional connections and warm, friendly relationships with each other. Through these spiritual connections and direct interactions, the warmth of the group’s atmosphere and its positive emotional environment are formed, which act as necessary and beneficial factors for speech development. These positive factors are created (often unnoticed by the members) through the use of special psychological techniques.

Methods

The initial level of language training does not matter much, since learning begins immediately with speech in its synthetic form, and everyone will be able to assimilate as much language material as he wants and as much as he will be given due to natural inclinations and abilities, which, however, will be greatly developed by everyone. In the case of our training, it is even better not to have preliminary knowledge, perhaps initially incorrect, in order to avoid painful breakage of their restructuring later. To adjust people's education to the same standard or, as is now customary, to the same age and “language” level is not only wrong, but also harmful. Imagine a calm sea - it splashes steadily and evenly, but there is no seething life in it, no development and growth of the water element. The same is true in education: neither an even and average level of knowledge, nor age uniformity can contribute and facilitate the achievement of great results.

But how does such a psychotherapeutic group create the speech environment from which a person draws language material and which, as we said, surrounds the child from the moment of birth? According to the modeling of the basic principles of ontogenetic speech development, such an environment in the form of sounding speech, filled with linguistic information, should surround adults from the first moment of learning in a group.

Result

The main source of information for this study is the teacher, who from the very first minute of class addresses the group in a foreign language. They do so with a quiet translation that is almost subconsciously understood by the students. This factor, which is often criticized by those who support direct or natural methods of learning without an intermediary language, accelerates the learning process and its pace. It allows adult learners to immediately understand the flow of spoken language. The translation should be almost invisible, like a shadow. It should not be word-for-word, but rather a synthesis of the entire foreign phrase or even entire sections of text. Its purpose is to convey the meaning of the statement and allow students to understand the uniqueness and authenticity of the foreign-language model, which often differs from their native tongue. This is necessary to prevent a literal translation from one language into another, which inevitably arises due to language interference - the imposition of a foreign system onto the native one and their intermingling. We consider it unacceptable to provide a text translated from Uzbek into a foreign language, as this leads to the translation model becoming fixed in the student’s mind, and in the future, on a subconscious level, they will continue to translate from Uzbek into that foreign language without trying to understand the new language. Moreover, their attention is not focused on the foreign language itself, but on the details of translation. For this reason, we do not use the G.Lozanovian “cradle” technique, which is well-known. It would seem that presenting language material in this way would contribute to better assimilation, but in practice, people accustomed to this

method become like addicts who constantly expect the translation to be repeated at least twice, and their brains become too lazy to work independently. We are trying to achieve a situation where one language system is independent of another, and they can exist side by side in the human brain. We don't believe that the complete removal of the native language from teaching is the only acceptable approach. In fact, this "natural" method takes years to master. It's no wonder that people who return from a two-week trip to England, where they try to learn a foreign language, complain that they spent those weeks just getting oriented and didn't learn anything. According to our training system, students start with a gentle and almost imperceptible introduction, which is provided by their native language.

Discussion

Here, it could be argued that the use of the native language in teaching, although "behind the scenes" and to a minimum extent, violates the natural course of human acquisition of speech. Although many bilingual children master two languages not simultaneously, but with some separation, the first language is still used to a certain extent to understand the second language. This is true, but we don't completely reproduce the development of speech in ontogenesis. We are only talking about a number of significant analogies and important principles, as well as a kind of modeling of its foundations. Like every model, it has the right to some tolerances. Additionally, since we rely on all our developed mental functions in adult education, it would be illogical and wrong to exclude our native speech from our powerful arsenal if it can still be useful in various ways. In our opinion, the interference of multilingual systems in the adult brain is inevitable, especially at the initial stages of learning a new language. Even if a learner is completely deprived of translation into their native language and learns only through visual means, their brain will still generate associations, comparisons, and analogies to the language system they already know. For people who speak multiple languages, this process is even more complex, as their brain produces a larger number of associations and analogies, helping them to learn a new language more easily and quickly. By presenting language material in a holistic and synthetic form (with the help of hints in the native language), we can ensure that involuntary analogies become more figurative, larger and more voluminous.

Acknowledgements

All our main textbooks for learning foreign languages are organized in a similar way: English, Uzbek for foreigners. This includes not only the initial passage of the text on the first day but also the entire language material. It is typically divided into 22 lessons of 4.5 hours each (100 hours total), taking place over seven-and-a-half weeks, three times per week, and, as life demands, in the evening. As practice shows, these classes and the number of hours spent studying in these conditions are optimal for our curriculum. They allow students not only to develop their speaking skills within the limits of the knowledge they have acquired, but also to maintain the freshness and energy of the classes until the very end. Completing classes with a feeling of accomplishment, before fatigue sets in, encourages students to continue working on their own. Of course, the amount of knowledge acquired is always individual and depends on the student's abilities and level of development. However, even the most "incapable" students never absorb less than one-third of the proposed material. According to mathematical calculations, this amounts to almost 1,800 lexical

units, which is more than enough to “feel comfortable in any situation and with a high probability...”. I understand your interlocutor's point of view. If a child takes several years to understand the system and structure of language and master speech, along with the development of all mental functions, then, relying on the existing functions of adults, stimulating and further developing them using special psychotherapeutic and psychocorrective methods, our teaching method based on integrative linguistic and psychological training can shorten this process to just a few weeks.

So, comprehension of foreign language by adults begins and takes place in a warm atmosphere of a “group-family” created by psychotherapeutic techniques, in a social environment. In addition, according to K.E. Rudestam, the group “turns out to be a microcosm, a society in miniature, reflecting the outside world and adding an ingredient of realism to artificially created interaction”. Education, with the assistance of psychological trainings, follows the model of the child’s speech and language development, i.e. according to the formula “understanding - speaking - reading – writing”. Here, as in childhood, a person begins to understand and speak first, and only then to read and write, naturally mastering practical and, as it were, “self-generating” grammar. Only after that, already fluent enough in speech, he can, at will, go to “school”, where he will be free to comprehend the grammatical wisdom of the language already in theory.

It should be noted that almost all the principles of building the educational process and a set of methodological tools have both an ontogenetic (by analogy with the development of speech in childhood) and a psychotherapeutic orientation, which does not contradict each other, but only complement each other.

Conclusions

The world is refracted in a person's consciousness through his own self. In childhood, such egocentrism manifests itself especially vividly when it seems to the little man that the universe revolves exclusively around him and for him. In our training, designed for adults, but whom we, imperceptibly for them with the help of special functional techniques, return to the level of childhood (what P.M. Granovskaya calls “functional infantilization” occurs), this “egocentric” factor must be taken into an account. This in no way means that we encourage the development of egocentrism (on the contrary, in the course of socio-psychological trainings we try to minimize it in a person's personality). In this case, we only use the presence of this natural factor as a natural support to increase the effectiveness of training. Rather, we turn this factor towards identification, i.e. self-identification of people with the presented characters, which allows you to skip both the text (and therefore the speech of the characters), and the events described in it, and all the actions that occur during training, regardless of role-playing transformations, through yourself. Very similar in meaning, although with a mirrored approach, is the statement of the American educator and scientist, developer of innovative training programs Eric Jensen that only when learning turns out to be personally directed, personally significant and perfectly woven into the canvas of the student's own life, it becomes truly interesting, deep and lasting for him.

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